

Quantitative Determination of the Strength of Activated Sludge Flocs in Biological Wastewater Treatment

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Abstract

One of characteristics of activated sludge flocs is its strength. Measurement of the floc strength is an important scientific and practical task while solving operational problems in biological wastewater treatment technology. Currently, at existing wastewater treatment plants this characteristic is determined visually that leads to subjectivity in the assessment. A computerized method for determining the floc strength by using the ImageJ program has been developed, based on both reference photos and D. Eikelboom's definitions, converted into a quantitative format. Quantitative values are ranked according to the developed scale. Measurement of the floc strength allows to evaluate and predict such operational characteristics as the sedimentation properties of activated sludge in secondary clarifiers and the ability to stick in membrane biological reactors.

Keywords

Biological wastewater treatment, activated sludge, technological characteristics, floc strength

INTRODUCTION

The ability of activated sludge to form strong, rapidly settling flocs is one of its key property, that is used for the process of biological wastewater treatment in “*aeration tank-secondary clarifier*” system (Chen *et al.* 2023; Eikelboom 2000; Karczmarczyk *et al.* 2022). Flocs formation is caused by bacteria in activated sludge microbiocenosis, secreting biopolymers-flocculants, those connect separate cells into aggregates (flocs) capable to grow in size and separate from the treated liquid. The activity of this process depends on many factors, e.g. microflora and microfauna species variety, oxygen conditions, physical and technical parameters, etc. (Eikelboom 2000; Yuan, Y. *et al.* 2010; Chu *et al.* 2004).

Important factors for sludge sedimentation are the morphological properties of its flocs (size, structure, strength (firmness), shape) and the state of filamentous microorganisms population (Eikelboom 2000; Karczmarczyk *et al.* 2022). Rounded flocs settle better than irregularly shaped ones; compact (robust) flocs settle faster than open clusters. Weak flocs can be easily damaged (Chu *et al.* 2004; Mesquita *et al.* 2016). Young activated sludge, which has not yet become compact and still contains large flocs, has low sedimentation capacity. Such sludge can usually be found in the aeration tank during start-up stage, as well as in case of fast sludge growth, when a significant amount of excess sludge was removed. While maturing, the flocs are becoming more compact, size is becoming bigger, a biopolymer gel is accumulating (this gel protects the floc cells from toxicants and retains microbial cells); thus, such flocs can be easily separated from the treated water in the secondary clarifiers (Eikelboom 2000; Mesquita *et al.* 2016, Jarvis *et al.* 2005, Yuan *et al.* 2010).

According to (Eikelboom 2000 - see Table 1), characteristics of flocs should be taken into account when establishing the sludge quality. However, such important quality indicators as structure, strength and shape are characterised not quantitatively, but only qualitatively during the activated sludge diagnostics proposed in (Eikelboom 2000). Such approach is applied for technical control of

treatment processes at existing wastewater treatment plants in Ukraine as well. Due to visual assessment of strength, such estimates are very subjective and not statistically processed.

Table 1. Criteria for determining the quality of activated sludge (from *Eikelboom 2000*).

Indicator	Good	Moderate	Poor
Floc structure	compact	open	-
Floc strength	compact, robust	weak	-
Floc shape	rounded	irregular	-

The aim of the research is to develop a method for quantitative evaluation of activated sludge flocs strength in wastewater treatment facilities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The object of the study is activated sludge from the aeration tank of municipal biological treatment facility. To quantify activated sludge characteristics, we used sludge micro-photographs processing in ImageJ software. Microscopic images of sludge were photographed at a magnification of 150 times when microscoping samples of stirred sludge liquid using a Lomo Mikmed-1 biological microscope. To scale the size of flocs for further studies, direct measurements of the floc size were performed in parallel using an eyepiece micrometer. Theoretical calculations and statistical processing of the experimental data were performed using the Microsoft Excel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To quantify the floc strength, we used the colour intensity and contrast indicators in the ImageJ software. The floc photographs from (*Eikelboom 2000*) were used as references for determining the strength. The calculations were based on photographs from (*Eikelboom 2000*) taken at 150x (50 pixels) magnification. These images were used to determine the colour intensity in the floc centre point (point 1), at the floc edge point (point 2) and the colour intensity of the water environment around the floc (point 3) (Fig. 1, Tables 2, 3). Contrast indicator was determined as the difference in colour intensity in floc points and water ($d(1-3)$), ($d(1-2)$) expressed in %.

Figure 1. Points on activated sludge for determining colour intensity and contrast indicators of flocs

Table 2. Determination of colour intensity and contrast indicators of robust flocs (with high strength) of activated sludge (photos from *Jarvis et al. 2005*), 150x magnification.

Measurement	Colour intensity in point			Contrast value			
	1	2	3	Absolute			Between the points 2-3, %
				d(1-2)	d(1-3)	d(2-3)	
1	126	240	146	114	20	94	39.17
2	182	222	147	40	35	7	33.78
3	167	202	138	35	29	64	31.68
4	137	214	138	77	1	76	35.51
5	131	167	129	36	2	38	22.75
6	195	91	132	104	63	41	45.05
7	128	215	140	87	12	75	34.88
8	127	156	131	29	4	25	16.03
9	144	220	146	76	2	74	33.64
10	140	193	138	53	2	55	28.5
11	128	221	136	93	8	85	38.46
Average value	147.7	192	138.5	65.1	17	54.9	32.677

Table 3. Determination of colour intensity and contrast indicators of weak flocs (with low strength) of activated sludge (photos from *Jarvis et al. 2005*), 150x magnification.

Measurement	Colour intensity in point			Contrast value			
	1	2	3	Absolute value			Between the points 2 and 3, %
				d(1-2)	d(1-3)	d(2-3)	
1	212	141	126	71	86	15	10,64
2	83	111	119	28	36	8	7.21
3	181	106	124	75	57	18	16.98
4	239	155	119	84	120	36	23.23
5	152	102	122	50	30	20	19.61
6	90	101	109	11	19	8	7.92
7	164	123	115	41	49	8	6.5
8	79	123	118	44	39	5	4.07
9	195	109	127	86	68	18	16.51
10	169	107	123	62	46	16	14.95
11	116	134	113	18	3	21	15.67
Average value	156.4	117.8	120.2	55.2	55	15.2	13.02

As can be seen, on average for the robust flocs, the contrast value between points 1 and 3 is 6.2%, and between points 2 and 3 is 27.9%. On average for the weak flocs, the contrast value between points 1 and 3 is 23.1%, and between points 2 and 3 is -2%. Thus, the contrast value between points 2 and 3 is more promising for our research aim. For separate samples, the contrast between these points for the robust flocs reached almost 33%, while for the weak flocs, it was 2.5 times less, valued at only 13%. This difference makes it possible to use the contrast gradient as an indicator of the strength of activated sludge flocs.

The algorithm for scale creation is based on calculations made for the reference samples. The scale was developed in 3 stages (Fig.2): (1). Establish the difference (a) in the contrast value (% , between points 2 and 3) between a robust floc (M) and a weak floc (m), integers: $33-13 = 20$ (%). (2). Set the scale step by dividing the difference (a) by 4 ($20/4 = 5$) and consider the range from $(m-a/4)$ to $(M+a/4)$, in our case from 8 to 38. (3). Build the scale step by step in increments of $a/4$. According to this scale, if the contrast ratio is $\leq 8\%$, the flocculation is very weak, from 8.1 to 18% - weak, from 18.1 to 28% - rather robust, from 28.1 to 38% - robust, and $\geq 38.1\%$ - very robust.

Figure 2. Construction of a scale of strength of activated sludge flocs by the value of constructability

Thus, the developed method for quantifying the strength of activated sludge flocs allows for detailing of the results of visual assessments and unify definitions by different specialists.

REFERENCES

- Chen, G., Ekama, G., van Loosdrecht, M., Brdjanovic, D. 2023 *Biological Wastewater Treatment: Principles, Modelling and Design*. IWA Publishing, London DOI: 10.2166/9781789060362
- Eikelboom, D. H. 2000 *Process Control of Activated Sludge Plants by Microscopic Investigation* (London: IWA Publishing) p 163
- Karczmarczyk, A., and Kowalik, W. 2022 Combination of microscopic tests of the activated sludge and effluent quality for more efficient on-site treatment *J. Water* **14** (3), 489 DOI: 10.3390/w14030489
- Yuan, Y., and Ramin, R. 2010 Strength and breakage of activated sludge flocs *J. Powder Technol.* **199** (2) 111–119 DOI: 10.1016/j.powtec.2009.11.021
- Chu, C., Lee, D. 2004 Structural analysis of sludge flocs *J. Adv. Powder Technol.* **15** 515–532 DOI: 10.1163/1568552042000246
- Mesquita, D., Amaral, A., Ferreira, E. 2016 Estimation of effluent quality parameters from an activated sludge system using quantitative image analysis *J. Chem Eng.* **285** 349–357 DOI: [10.1016/j.cej.2015.09.110](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2015.09.110)
- Jarvis, P., Jefferson, B., Gregory, J., Parsons, S. 2005 A review of floc strength and breakage *J. Water Res.* **39** (14) 3121–3137 DOI: 10.1016/j.watres.2005.05.022

Acknowledgements: We gratefully acknowledge the financial support provided by the project StormCompetence - Strengthening researchers' professional competencies on stormwater management for renovation of UA city infrastructure in the post-war time (funded by the Swedish Institute). This work has been conducted as a part of the Stormwater&Sewers research cluster, financed by Svenskt Vatten (Swedish Water and Wastewater Association).